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DEMO+

Bottom-up democracy in the EU and globally: Driving forward?

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Between *Infinitude* and *Indifference*:

The Anthropolitics of Extraction in Australia and the Global Southeast

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&

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The Hegemony of Extraction

Australia ('Lucky Country'): Nature

- World's third largest exporter of fossil fuels, behind Russia and Saudi Arabia, the largest exporter of coking coal, used in steel manufacturing, the second largest exporter of thermal coal, used in coal-fired power stations, and the second largest exporter of liquefied gas (USA: 102.3 vs Australia: 81.8 million metric tons per year).

Southeast Asia ('Continent of Labour*'): Human

- Labour in Southeast Asia is defined by massive intra-regional migration and a deep reliance on Global Supply Chains (GSCs), with an estimated 75 million workers linked to export-oriented industries. While the region experiences rapid economic growth, workers frequently face precarious conditions, including wage suppression, informal employment, and restricted union freedoms. [[1](#), [2](#)].
- More than one in four workers in the region is directly tied to GSCs in sectors such as garments, electronics, and automotive manufacturing.
- Women make up a large portion of the informal and manufacturing sectors, frequently encountering wage inequality, lack of social protections, and workplace discrimination.

Source: ILO (latest); * Chang, D.- o. 2015. "From global factory to continent of labour: labour and development in Asia". *Asian Labour Review* 1 (1): 1– 48.

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■ CHRONIQUE INTERNATIONALE DE L'IRES

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■ Numéro spécial Les syndicats face aux défis environnementaux

Retour

La pollution des eaux, des terres et de l'air, le réchauffement climatique ou encore l'érosion de la biodiversité sont le résultat d'un système économique fondé sur une croissance illimitée et indifférente à ses effets sur la nature. Face à cette réalité qui affecte les travailleuses et les travailleurs du Nord et du Sud, quelles stratégies les syndicats censés les représenter adoptent-ils ?

Ce numéro spécial de la Chronique internationale de l'IRES s'efforce d'éclairer cette question à partir de l'examen de sept cas nationaux (Belgique, Suède, Allemagne, Argentine, États-Unis, Canada, Australie), et du cas européen à travers le rôle joué par la Confédération européenne des syndicats (CES). Il montre la grande diversité des discours et attitudes des syndicats vis-à-vis des questions environnementales, allant du déni jusqu'au soutien de la « justice environnementale ».

L'examen de cas précis dans chaque pays permet de mettre en évidence les nombreux facteurs qui déterminent les stratégies syndicales : période concernée, insertion du pays dans les chaînes mondiales de valeur, système de relations professionnelles, orientation idéologique du syndicat, liens avec d'autres acteurs (employeurs, associations écologistes, mouvements sociaux, communautés des peuples autochtones)...

Ce numéro souhaite ainsi contribuer à la réflexion qui, du moins en France, a commencé à voir le jour à partir du milieu des années 2010 avec plusieurs publications s'intéressant aux rapports entre syndicalisme et environnement ou entre travail et écologie.

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Climate Policy under Labor: focus on net zero

- The Australian Government has made a firm commitment to drive Australia's transition to net zero.
- Australia has enshrined in law its targets of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 43% from 2005 levels by 2030 and net zero by 2050. It is taking a whole-of-government approach to drive towards those targets including new funding streams and investment in underpinning infrastructure.
- This is backed by an Australian Government investment of \$24.9 billion over this decade to deliver climate change and energy transformation priorities, including
 - Transforming Australia's electricity supply to run mainly on renewables
 - Supporting the development of new, clean energy industries
 - Supporting the decarbonisation of existing industries and transport network
- <https://www.globalaustralia.gov.au/industries/net-zero>

Climate
policies
reaching
Unions'
demands

Labor's initiatives, the *National Energy Transition Authority Bill 2022* (effective March 2023) and the *National Net-Zero Authority* later in July, reflected demands from the ACTU Congress 2021.

- See: A safe climate with good union jobs (Policy 10) <https://bit.ly/49fB5QJ>

ACTU Action Plan 2020-2025 <https://bit.ly/3QBWb4t>

1

- Work with the international union movement to ensure that Australia joins the global community in adopting national emissions targets that are ambitious and based on science, and national policy and programs to achieve these targets in a manner which maximises the benefits, and minimizes any hardship created by the shift to net zero emissions.

2

- Establishing a national Energy Transition Authority to plan and coordinate retirement of Australia's coal-fired power plants; ensure workers at these facilities are trained and redeployed in secure, decent jobs and that there are no forced redundancies; and ensure that new jobs and industries are created in regions disproportionately impacted by the shift to net zero emissions.

3

- Ensuring that new low carbon industries such as renewable energy, recycling and environmental restoration are built on sustainable foundations by providing secure and safe unionised jobs with fair wages and conditions.

4

- Ensuring that Australia is at the forefront of industries that are emerging to solve the climate crisis such as hydrogen, green steel and renewable energy powered manufacturing and minerals processing, and that these industries are developed in a manner that creates secure, high quality jobs for Australian workers.

5

- Ensuring that workers voices and union perspectives are incorporated in climate and energy policy as it is developed by governments and business.

6

- Support workers to take collective action in their workplaces to minimize the workplace impacts of global warming, and to drive emissions reductions and environmental improvements in their workplace.

See also:

*Energy Transition Authority:
What Workers Need*

- Why: The Need for a federal Energy Transition Authority
- How: Principles for a Best Practice Just Transition
- What: Remit and Structure of an Energy Transition Authority
- <https://www.actu.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/energy-transition-authority-what-workers-need-actu.pdf>

A strong
commitment
from the ACTU,
but then...

- Federations are divided along the union spectrum and there are internal dissonances: a matter for future research.

A selection of key (recent) references:

- Markey R., McIvor J. (2019), « Australian workers' climate action: Constraints and opportunities », *International Union Rights*, vol. 26, n° 4, p. 10-11, <https://doi.org/10.1353/iur.2019.a838166>.
- Mildenberger M. (2020), *Carbon Captured: How Business and Labor Control Climate Politics*, Cambridge, London, MIT Press.
- Wright C., Irwin R., Nyberg D., Bowden V. (2022), « "We're in the coal business": Maintaining fossil fuel hegemony in the face of climate change », *Journal of Industrial Relations*, vol. 64, n° 4, p. 544-563, <https://doi.org/10.1177/00221856211070632>.

Stepping away from the fossil fuel ideology?

“So, we are in a hard place. Naïve optimism about an easy, cheap transition to net zero is at risk of giving way to brutal negativity that it’s all just too hard”. T. Wood, Why Australia urgently needs a climate plan and a Net Zero National Cabinet Committee to implement it, *The Conversation*, 10 octobre 2023, <https://bit.ly/3SkjLnB>.

- P. Menon, « Analysis: Australia’s climate policies don’t match its big talk at COP27 », *Reuters*, November 20, 2022, <https://bit.ly/40fpfC2>.
- Australia’s coal exports create almost two and a half times the emissions Australians produce domestically. P. Martin, « What is the point of moving to net zero on the latter while we do nothing on coal exports? », *The Conversation*, 29 octobre 2023, <https://bit.ly/3MAaX9L>
- *Phasing down or phasing up? Top fossil fuel producers plan even more extraction despite climate promises*, Production Gap Report 2023, <https://bit.ly/47aZ0zs>
- Global report highlights “enormous chasm” between government rhetoric and climate action », The Australian Institute, November 8, 2023, <https://bit.ly/47DuSwD>

Infinitude and Indifference

From Extraction to Escalation

<https://www.humanrights.unsw.edu.au/sites/default/files/documents/2024%20Escalation%20Report%20%5Bv7%5D.pdf>

In 2023–24, Australian governments provided [\\$14.5 billion in subsidies](https://australiainstitute.org.au/post/fossil-fuel-subsidies/) to coal mines, oil and gas operations and major fossil fuel users. (<https://australiainstitute.org.au/post/fossil-fuel-subsidies/>)

Contention: *Not necessarily about less; but rather how to make more out of it!*

A National Plebiscite for a 25% Gas Export Tax

(<https://gas-plebiscite.australiainstitute.org.au/>)

Labour & Value Chains in the Global Southeast

(forthcoming: E. Lafaye de Micheaux, S. Le Queux, M. Perisse and M. Serrano (eds.), Palgrave Singapore)

- There is a (sometimes extremely) low labour income share amidst economic growth;
- The legal framework is usually favourable to workers, but inept and poorly enforced, albeit exception; Labour representation is fraught with ambiguity and trade unions often co-opted and complicit;
- Demographics matter: there is a prevalence of a massive industrial reserve army to tap into, including internal (rural) and regional migrant labour and a resulting hyper-exploitation of these workers; Development is labour centric and labour intensive;
- Integration in global value chains is determinant but with undetermined and uneven outcomes in relation to labour and value extraction.

Labour in the nexus of Accumulation and Hegemony in the Global Southeast (*ibid*)

Labour & Value Chains in the Global Southeast

(forthcoming: E. Lafaye de Micheaux, S. Le Queux, M. Perisse and M. Serrano (eds.), Palgrave Singapore)

- A case of *multi-scalar* and *uneven* development, which (...) ‘does not result in social advancement for workers but rather in the continuous reconfiguration of social fragmentation’ (Hurtgen and al., 2025: 11).

<https://jep-journal.com/ausgabe/multiscalar-uneven-development-and-the-socio-spatial-fragmentation-of-labour/>

- The more integration into global value chains and the more partition within the system: i.e. *the process of (labour) value extraction comes through system extraction.*
- the development ‘ladder’ is indeed a *folding* ladder, with as a result a multi-layering of labour and a blurring of class which has arguably consequences in hindering the capacity to idealise, organise and activate contention.
- Better described as a context of *sliding* scales: ‘a continuous loop of chains’.

Infinitude and Indifference

“Inequality *in* development is inseparable from the development *of* inequality”
(Edgar Morin, *Introduction à une politique de l’homme*, 1965)

How then conceive space and scope for counter-hegemony?

- Democracy is the obvious header, but not to avail;
- In a context that is heavily labour dependent, labour *agitation* is part of the answer;
- There is partition, but no dislocation: chains are chains indeed. And scales need brackets (conditions to FDIs and social clauses in FTAs for example). Disruption targeting these brackets may prove successful in strategically derailing the intertwined logics of hegemony and accumulation, but to which extent to structurally matter?

Infinitude and Indifference

From extraction to exhaustion

Bottom-up activism and exogenous pressures are necessary, but not sufficient. At best, the most predictable outcome would be some form of concessions in the political exchange; yet again with relative winners and a bulk of losers in a **class trample-like balancing scenario**.

In a way that mirrors the rise of populism elsewhere, we witness a situation wherein there is instead mounting support for the oligarchies, whatever in the form of chauvinist nationalism or corporatism, in support for the status-quo and order.

Odds are not for a change of order in the Global Southeast; they are rather towards a secularisation and deepening of the dynamics at play – which is the very essence of hegemony – **from extraction into exhaustion**.